

In-flight Port Environment Experience with VDES R-Mode

M. Wirsing, A. Dammann, R. Raulefs Institute of Communications and Navigation
German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany

Email: {Markus.Wirsing, Armin.Dammann, Ronald.Raulefs}@DLR.de

Abstract—The use of an aircraft for vessels in ports could be crucial in emergency situations to save lives, and ensures cargo and valuable equipment can be recovered safely. The aircraft therefore helps to improve the situational awareness on the ground and in the air. VDES R-Mode is an alternative positioning, navigation and time (PNT) system to complement navigation information, primarily to support the maritime traffic. We describe a measurement campaign of VDES R-Mode signals transmitted in the port of Hamburg and received on an airplane flying at an altitude of about 400 m above the port of Hamburg. Further, we compare the positioning performance achieved in the urban environment of the port with that of GNSS. We found that we were able to achieve an accuracy better than 204 m 95% of the time despite encountering interference from other signals.

Index Terms—VDES, R-Mode, APNT.

I. INTRODUCTION

Alternative position, navigation and timing (APNT) systems provide vital information to increase the resilience on operations in case the global navigation satellite systems (GNSSs) are jammed or even spoofed. VDES R-Mode [2] has been described by IALA as an alternative PNT solution for the marine systems onboard of a vessel especially to complement the satellite based GNSSs in case of disturbances. It is based on the VHF Data Exchange System; a recently standardised communication system for maritime applications that extends the well known Automatic Identification System (AIS) [1]. VDES R-Mode is an extension of this communication system for positioning purposes. A known ranging signal conforming to the VDES standard is transmitted from multiple transmitter stations at precisely known time instances. Based on time of arrival measurements and multilateration, it is possible to determine the position at the receiver.

In 2021 [3] a measurement campaign in Bavaria allowed for the first time to assess the positioning performance with three synchronized base stations and a vessel on the lake Ammer. The performance analysis showed positioning performances with an error in the range between 10 m and 100 m. It is vital to assess the performances in various conditions, and to include other participants in the marine environment, such as aircrafts.

Recently, GNSS jamming incidents have occurred with increased frequency. Especially the Baltic sea area near Russian territories has been affected. This jamming does not only affect ships, but even more so airplanes. Due to their high altitude, they can be jammed by far away signal sources. Nonetheless,

airplanes nowadays often rely on GPS for performing the approach to their destination airport. One example that has received a lot of publicity is Tartu Airport, where scheduled flights were suspended for a month due to jamming.

APNT solutions typically address the requirements within a specific domain, such as maritime or aeronautical contexts. In a coordinated maritime search and rescue (SAR) operation involving both nearby ships and an aerial unit, effective communication and cooperation are crucial. Consequently, the SAR aircraft employs maritime communication systems, such as the Automatic Identification System (AIS) or, in the future, the VHF Data Exchange System (VDES). All units, whether in the water or in the air, depend on the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) for accurate positioning. However, GNSS is susceptible to jamming, the effectiveness of which depends on the received power of the jamming signal. This power is influenced by the propagation conditions between the transmitter and receiver. The range of a jamming signal is significantly affected by the antenna heights of both the transmitter and receiver above the water surface. Therefore, aircraft are particularly vulnerable to jamming compared to vessels due to their higher antenna elevation.

It is therefore desirable to have a backup positioning source available for aircraft as well. In this paper, we outline a measurement campaign to assess the performance of VDES R-Mode on board of an aircraft in typical operational heights of a SAR plane.

Fig. 1. The wingpod with the VHF receiver.

$r_{0.0}^{100}$	$r_{0.3}^{100}$	$r_{0.7}^{100}$	$r_{1.0}^{100}$	x^{25}	a	$a_{0.2}^+$	$a_{0.4}^+$	$a_{0.6}^+$	$a_{0.8}^+$	$a_{1.0}^+$
-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	----------	-----	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

Fig. 2. The sequence of signals transmitted by each base station.

Fig. 3. The range estimates to each of the three base stations.

Fig. 4. The estimated relative speeds between each of the base stations and the receiver.

II. MEASUREMENTS

To practically assess the performance of VDES R-Mode for aeronautical applications, we performed a measurement campaign in the area of the harbour Hamburg.

A. Measurement setup

The measurement setup consisted of three VDES R-Mode transmitters at different locations in Hamburg. Each of the transmitters consisted of an Ettus USRP B210 software defined radio to generate the VDES signals, a power amplifier with an output power of 10 W, and a GNSS-disciplined oscillator to provide an accurate timing reference. The three transmitter sites were:

- The building of the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH) in Hamburg St. Pauli
- An office building of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Hamburg Finkenwerder.
- The building of the Fraunhofer Center for Maritime Logistics and Services (CML) in Hamburg Harburg

The receiver also consisted of an Ettus USRP B210 software defined radio together with a small form factor computer. The receiver also had an integrated GPS disciplined oscillator that provided an accurate timing reference. The receiver was mounted in the wingpod of a research airplane, together with other scientific payloads. The wingpod with the receiver can be seen in Figure 1 A small Ettus VERT400 antenna was used for the receiver, mounted on the bottom of the wingpod. The

route of the airplane is shown in Figure 8.

B. Transmitted signal

Each base station transmitted a number of different signals. Among them:

- A 100 kHz VDES R-Mode signal r_γ^{100} with $\gamma \in \{0.0, 0.3, 0.7, 1.0\}$
- A 25 kHz VDES R-Mode signal r^{25}
- A standard AIS signal a
- An AIS+ signal a_{dA}^+ with $dA \in \{0.2, 0.4, \dots, 1.0\}$

Figure 2 shows which signals were transmitted. The transmitted AIS signal and its AIS+ variations are mentioned for completeness, but are out of scope for this article.

The parameter γ for the VDES R-Mode signal is a design parameter between 0 and 1 that influences the spectrum of the signal. Lower values of γ cause a more uniform spectrum, while higher values cause a spectrum with most of the signal energy at the edge of the spectrum. The optimal value of γ depends on the Signal to Noise Ratio at the receiver [4].

C. Data Evaluation

In order to evaluate the data, a maximum likelihood approach was used for estimating the delay τ and the Doppler shift Δf of the received signal.

$$(\hat{\tau}, \hat{\Delta f}) = \arg \max_{\tau, \Delta f} \sum_k x[k] \cdot s^*(kT_s - \tau) e^{j2\pi k T_s \Delta f} \quad (1)$$

with $x[k]$ being the received samples from the software defined radio receiver, and $s(t)$ being the transmitted signal. A numerical optimization method was used to evaluate the $\arg \max$ operation. From the estimated time of arrival, a range r was estimated as

$$\hat{r} = c_0 \cdot (\hat{\tau} - \tau_{\text{offset}}). \quad (2)$$

With c_0 being the speed of light, and τ_{offset} being an experimentally determined offset parameter. As described in section II-B, multiple R-Mode signals with different parameters of the parameter γ were transmitted. For this article, we evaluated the signals with $\gamma = 0.7$. The results of the range estimation can be seen in Figure 3, and the results of the speed estimation in Figure fig:speeds. Implausible negative range estimates were discarded. Other outliers were not removed.

The estimated range \hat{r} and the estimated Doppler shift $\hat{\Delta f}$ for each station are then used to track the position with an unscented Kalman filter. The Kalman filter was initialized with the true position and velocity that was obtained from the GNSS reference. The estimated track after Kalman filter tracking can be seen in Figure 8.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the results of the range estimation, that are shown in Figure 3, we observe a few obvious outliers, such as shortly before 09:00 in the CML range. We observed that some of these outliers correlated with interference events that were noticeable in the received signal. Figure 5 shows an example where the first third of one second is affected by interference. We have not yet identified the source of the interference

Fig. 5. An example of interference affecting part of the ranging signal. The evaluated time slots are marked red.

Fig. 6. The absolute error of the position estimation over time.

events. Obviously implausible outliers that resulted in negative range estimates were discarded after estimation, otherwise no measures were taken to identify or reject outliers in the measurements.

Figure 7 shows the distribution of the absolute estimation error after Kalman filter tracking. It can be seen from that figure that the error was below 204 m for 95 % of the time. It can also be seen that errors up to 470 m were observed during the measurement.

In Figure 6, the absolute error can be seen over the course of the measurement. We can see that errors above 250 m only occurred during a few instances. Many of the increases in the absolute error also correlate to outlier events that are visible in the range or speed measurements. It is therefore plausible that the accuracy can be improved further by introducing plausibility checks and rejecting outlier measurements that might have been affected by interference.

In previous measurements, we observed that including Doppler observations in the tracking of the position, significantly improved its accuracy [5]. Since the observed relative speeds in an aeronautical scenario are much higher than the speeds in a typical maritime scenario, we expect the influence of the Doppler observations to be even more important. Indeed, we can see that the most larger positioning errors occur at times where a significant error in the speed estimates can be seen in Figure 4.

Fig. 7. The distribution of the positioning error.

Fig. 8. The flightpath of the motorglider. The GNSS reference track is shown in Yellow. The R-Mode estimation is shown in red. The transmitter stations are shown as colored diamonds. CML in blue, DLR in red, and BSH in green.

IV. CONCLUSION

VDES R-Mode is a part of an alternative PNT system that eases the single dependency on GNSS in the maritime domain. For the first time, we applied VDES R-Mode to an aeronautical application and performed a flight measurement campaign over the harbour of Hamburg that demonstrates the feasibility of utilizing VDES R-Mode for aeronautical applications. We analyzed the received signals to estimate ranges and Doppler information. Using these data, we were able to track the airplanes position with an Unscented Kalman filter. We found that the achieved positioning accuracy was better than 204 m for 95 % of the time. We also found that the estimated position is occasionally affected by outliers in the range and Doppler measurements that are probably caused by interference. We expect that further accuracy improvements are possible if interference events are detected and affected measurements discarded.

The performed measurement campaign shows that it is feasible to utilize VDES R-Mode not only for maritime positioning, but also for airplanes.

REFERENCES

- [1] ITU-R Recommendation M.2092: Technical characteristics for a VHF data exchange system in the VHF maritime mobile band, 2022.
- [2] IALA, *G1158: VDES R-Mode, ed. 1.0*, <https://www.iala-aism.org/product/g1158/>, 2020
- [3] M. Wirsing, A. Dammann, R. Raulefs, *VDES R-Mode performance analysis and experimental results*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sat.1424>, 2021
- [4] M. Wirsing, A. Dammann, and R. Raulefs, "Designing a Ranging Signal for use with VDE R-Mode," in *2020 IEEE/ION Position, Location and Navigation Symposium (PLANS)*. IEEE, April 2020, pp. 822–826.
- [5] M. Wirsing and A. Dammann and R. Raulefs, "On the Positioning Performance of VDES R-Mode" in *Navigation 2021*, Edinburgh, United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.48448/tqtc-j579>, 2021